

The arc length of logarithm functions

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We view the following figure:

We search the arc length of this function. The general formula in the plane can be written:

$$L = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \sqrt{1 + f'(x)^2} \, dx$$

The function has got the form:

$$f(x) = a \cdot \ln(m \cdot x) \quad a, m > 0$$

with the differentiation: $f'(x) = \frac{a}{x}$

The general arc length of natural logarithm functions:

$$L = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{a}{x}\right)^2} \, dx$$

To the arc length it is valid:

$$L = \left[\sqrt{x^2 + a^2} + \frac{a}{2} \ln \left(C \cdot \frac{\sqrt{x^2 + a^2} - a}{\sqrt{x^2 + a^2} + a} \right) \right]_{x_1}^{x_2}$$

C is a integration constant.

This integral is determined at Gröbner [1] p.46 number 5k.

Reference:

[1] : Wolfgang Gröbner and Nikolaus Hofreiter „Integraltafel erster Teil“
Springer Verlag Wien 1975